
IMPORTANCE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING INDEPENDENT EDUCATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7353637>

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ABSTRACT

We cannot imagine today without television and the Internet. Television and the Internet form the basis of the field of journalism. So, the field of journalism is important in everyone's life. Understanding the true meaning of this word is the first most important step to enter the field of journalism. In today's rapidly developing media space, the field of Journalism and the tasks of a journalist are increasing. As the flow of the Internet is increasing, a great responsibility is placed on the shoulders of this field.

Keywords: *Journalism, education, upbringing, independent education, world experience.*

The modern renewal of all aspects of society's life creates the need to revise and organize the educational process at the university in the direction of increasing the role of independent work of students, developing their initiative and increasing responsibility for learning [Muslimova, A.F, 2010]. In such conditions, independent work becomes the priority form of the educational process, the purpose of which is to study the educational material more deeply and better. At the present time, it is necessary to have initiative, selflessness and business acumen in the performers of unique, equal to the value, reputation and prestige of education.

Success in education is mostly on the side of those who act boldly. Bold action is due to courage. School can give knowledge and enlightenment to a person, as stated by Abdulla Avloni, a classic representative of Uzbek national pedagogy.

In other countries that have built their training systems based on the number of contact or training hours, implementation has become more complicated. Initially, these countries mainly used the following approach: allocating credits to courses was based on the number of teaching hours for each subject.

This approach is based on the assumption that the number of teaching hours more or less reflects the student's workload. However, in practice this is not always the case. For example, experiences in Italy and Spain show that this approach is not satisfactory in the long run. The same study load may correspond to different student loads. In a number of countries, the situation is complicated because the content of the curricula is largely decided at the level of the central government: there is a clear list of subjects to be taught. This approach leads to more rigid structures and the fair distribution of credits becomes problematic [Orinov V, 2020].

Modern society sets increasingly high demands on the quality of education, requires personal qualities such as positive orientation, creativity, initiative, competence, competitiveness and professionalism from the future specialist. In modern conditions, personal characteristics such as analytical ability, a broad outlook, determination, confidence, the ability to take reasonable risks, a highly developed sense of reality, emotional stability, the ability to work in conditions of lack of information and time. to have value. Recently, the tasks of forming the intellectual potential of the nation and educating a person who can effectively use his creative potential have been defined as a priority task. The integration of international relations, the growing demand for highly qualified specialists who can independently identify and solve problems, sets the task of training well-rounded, creatively thinking specialists for higher educational institutions. The emergence of opportunities to study and work abroad also requires the need to optimize the educational process in order to improve the quality of education, develop the intellectual level and creative potential of a person [Shepherd I.P., Argunova T.G, 2010].

In conclusion, organization of students' independent work requires a complex approach, so new developments are needed to fully realize the creative potential not only of the student, but also of the teacher. The task of such developments is to help teachers organize independent work and students to learn learning material independently, to search for new knowledge, to acquire the ability to constantly study, to diligently master the culture of intellectual work.

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